

INNOVATIVE IDEAS AND METHODS IN TEACHING CHINESE LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *In the modern world, information technologies have become an integral part of all spheres of our lives. This tendency also affects the educational system. Teachers, including those who teach Chinese Languages, are introducing various modern tools in the educational process, which make help to make learning more effective.*

Keywords: *chinese Language, game, innovative technology, technological means, methods, techniques.*

ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ И МЕТОДЫ В ОБУЧЕНИИ КИТАЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В современном мире информационные технологии стали неотъемлемой частью всех сфер нашей жизни. Эта тенденция затрагивает и систему образования. Преподаватели, в том числе преподаватели китайского языка, внедряют в учебный процесс различные современные средства, помогающие сделать обучение более эффективным.*

Ключевые слова: *китайский язык, игра, инновационная технология, технологические средства, приемы, приемы.*

INTRODUCTION

After the independence of our country, the interest in teaching Chinese Languages has increased and many opportunities have been created for young people. As the first President Islam Karimov said, "At present, great importance is attached to the teaching of Chinese Languages in our country. This, of course, is not in vain. Today, there is no need to underestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of Chinese Languages for our countries, which are striving to take a worthy place in the world community, for our people, who are building their great future in cooperation with our foreign partners.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

"The demand for learning a Chinese Language is growing day by day. Chinese Language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening comprehension, and speaking), each of which provides specific insights and skills. Educational technology is the effective use of modern information technology in the educational process. It also aims to improve the quality and effectiveness of education through the introduction of modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages to using such information and communication technologies in learning a Chinese Language. For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. The use of modern technologies in the educational process is also an important factor for students to be familiar with and use information and communication technologies. One of the most effective ways is to teach and learn a Chinese Language using modern technology. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a Chinese Language;
- It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in Chinese Languages and TV programs;
- use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are more traditional methods;
- CD players are available.

RESEARCH RESULT

The use of these tools makes the process of learning a Chinese Language more interesting and effective for students. Today, interactive games are becoming a tradition in schools. It is well known that a variety of play-based activities help students demonstrate their abilities, focus, increase their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. In short, the use of innovative methods in English lessons develops students' logical thinking skills, fluency, and the ability to respond quickly and accurately. Such methods stimulate the student's desire for knowledge. The student tries to prepare well for the lessons. This makes students active participants in the learning process. As the education system sets itself the task of nurturing a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future we will contribute to the further development of effective use of innovative technologies by future teachers.

During the practical course, it is appropriate to use the appropriate applications when training to write hieroglyphs, they will help the student purposefully analyze what features the hieroglyph consists of (some applications, when writing out the hieroglyph, call the features aloud, indicate the main key), pay attention to proportions that are not always accurately presented in the printed materials offered in the textbook; some students are also hindered by the insufficient font size in manuals. In the application, if necessary, you can quickly check the order of strokes, the proportions of a particular character.

It is also appropriate to use the possibilities of the Internet to refer to explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language and reference books to replenish the background knowledge of the student. In particular, already in the first lessons of the textbook "A Practical Course of the Chinese Language" edited by A.F. Kondrashevsky, there is a poem by the poet of the Tang Dynasty Li Bo (Chinese Li Bai, 701-762/763), as well as a Chinese folk song "Jasmine flowers"[1].

DISCUSSION

It is quite possible to use the relevant video or audio recordings on the sites and listen to this song during the lesson, which, no doubt, enlivens the lesson. Among the background knowledge of sites required in the search, such popular search engines as Google or Baidu should be mentioned. At a later stage of training, the authors recommend the latter. This is due to the fact that Google is blocked in China, and the Chinese segment of this system is filled with a small number of Chinese who bypass these blocks. More often these are Chinese immigrants or Chinese students outside the PRC, as well as foreigners studying Chinese. For video and audio recordings, the Youtube website, where you can search for relevant recordings. However, mainland Chinese do not have the opportunity to use this site, there are also similar Chinese portals, such as tudou.com, youku.com and others. At the present stage, there are a lot of tools for teaching Chinese. The student can additionally use communication with native speakers via Skype, independent reading of newspapers and books, including on the Internet, and watching videos.

To improve the level of the language, acquire new knowledge and information, as well as to obtain aesthetic pleasure, it is appropriate to watch videos in the classroom, both educational and non-educational. Of course, it should be borne in mind that there should not be too many words unfamiliar to the student, and watching films in the classroom should be methodically well-built.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I would like to note that the experience presented in this article is not something radically new. Most Chinese language teachers, if they have the opportunity to use the Internet in class, intuitively come to such methods and, to one degree or another, use the capabilities of modern information technologies, since at the current stage it is impossible not to use them.

As for the various Internet programs for learning Chinese, in our opinion, they can only be recommended as additional tools. The textbook and traditional types of work under the guidance of a teacher are still the main ones in teaching. However, it is known that the success of a student depends to a greater extent on himself, according to the wonderful expression of one of the respected teachers of the Chinese language with a great work experience: "You cannot teach, you can only learn." And in this case, almost all means are good.

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